

WETTABILITY EVALUATION OF ACETYLATED FLAX AND KRAFT FIBERS USING THE DROP SHAPE METHOD

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Keywords: *Natural fiber composites, Acetylation, Wettability, Flax, Kraft fibers, Epoxy*

1 Introduction

Most studies dealing with the treatment of natural fibers, for their application in composites, focus on the enhancement of interfacial properties between the fibers and matrix [1]. Very few studies are dedicated to the direct measurement of the wettability of treated fibers by a liquid resin. This should be a concern considering that wettability is a crucial factor for molding, especially when porous natural fibers are used.

Several natural fiber treatments have been evaluated in the literature [2]. Among them, acetylation has been used to modify or enhance cellulose properties [3]. Recently, acetylated natural fibers have been used in composites to improve the mechanical properties of the fiber and the adhesion at the fiber/matrix interface [4]. Acetylation is also known to enhance the dimensional stability of composites and the surface roughness of cellulose fibers [4]. Recently, many studies have been conducted to determine the acetylation reaction parameters that would give an inexpensive, easy to implement and green synthesis pathway that could be used in the industry [5].

Acetylation of cellulose is relatively simple (Fig. 1). Acetic anhydride reacts with hydroxyl (-OH) groups on the cellulose in presence of an acid catalyst. One of the most common ways to acetylate cellulosic fibers is to use toluene as solvent and perchloric acid as catalyst [4, 6]. It has been shown that perchloric acid is more efficient than sulfuric acid [7]. Another way to acetylate cellulose fibers is to soak them for 2 hours into pure liquid acetic anhydride at 120°C [8]. This treatment is interesting because it does not require any solvent and the only reaction byproduct is acetic acid, a molecule that can be used in a variety of applications. Another solvent free treatment consists in soaking cellulose fibers into

acetic anhydride where a catalytic quantity of sulfuric acid has previously been added [5]. The reaction time can range from 6 to 24 hours, but an optimal time of 24 hours has been proposed [5]. This treatment is interesting because, in addition to being solvent free, it does not require any heating. It is very low cost and gives a high yield. Moreover, the required quantity of anhydride is low. A weight ratio of 1:10, with respect to fibers, is sufficient. The only drawback to this method is the long reaction time.

Another concern regarding natural fiber treatments is the drying process. For most treatments, the fibers need to be pre-dried, which increases the process cost. Some studies showed that moisture could be beneficial during the acetylation reaction [9]. When acetic anhydride comes in contact with water, the anhydride is hydrolyzed into acid. Depending on the moisture content, only a fraction of the anhydride present is converted into acetic acid which acts as catalyst. Acetic acid also causes fiber swelling, allowing the penetration of acetic anhydride inside the fibers to enhance the reaction with hydroxyl groups. An optimal moisture level of 5 to 7% was identified in the literature [6].

Since acetic anhydride reacts with hydroxyl groups, acetylated fibers contains less of these chemical functions and therefore exhibit a reduced hydrophilic character. Wettability tests using the drop shape method have been performed on acetylated fibers and it has been shown that the contact angle of water with cellulose fibers can be raised from 33° to 115° after acetylation [7].

In this work, acetylation has been realized on flax and softwood kraft fibers (produced for the manufacturing of paper) to evaluate how the treatment affects the wettability to liquid epoxy resin of both types of fibers. The long term objective behind this treatment is to develop a reinforcement

made of a layer of unidirectional (UD) flax fibers deposited on a thin layer of paper used as a binder and support for the flax fibers. Such reinforcement would be eventually produced with high volume papermaking processes. Our immediate objective was to find a method to measure the wettability of kraft and flax fibers and evaluate the acetylation treatment for kraft and flax fibers using different solvents and testing conditions. In addition to being effective at improving the mechanical and physical properties of composites, this treatment could have a positive effect on the overall permeability of the reinforcement by improving its wettability.

The drop shape method was used under different conditions to determine the efficiency of the acetylation treatment. In this method, a small droplet of resin is deposited over a pellet of compacted fibers and the contact angle at the base of the droplet is measured. By comparing angles measured on treated and untreated fibers, the effect of the treatment on the wettability of the fibers can be evaluated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Reagents and starting materials

The fibers used for this study were untreated flax obtained from Safilin (Sczytno, Poland) and bleached softwood kraft pulp obtained from Kruger Wayagamack (Trois-Rivières, Canada). Acetic anhydride (ACS reagent grade, $\geq 98\%$ purity) was supplied by Sigma Aldrich. The flax fibers were directly taken from a roll and cut into smaller pieces for handling and mixing.

2.2 Fiber conditioning

It is well known that water plays an important role in the acetylation reaction of cellulose. However, there is no consensus on the amount of water that may be present in the starting material without affecting the reaction yield. Consequently, we decided to perform the acetylation reaction of fibers at two different humidity levels: oven dried at 100°C for 24h and air dried (6-8% humidity). After 24h, the oven dried fibers were placed in a desiccator so no humidity uptake occurred.

2.3 Acetylation of fibers

The acetylation reaction was performed in heterogeneous conditions without any solvent according to the method described in [5]. 1 g of fibers was taken out the desiccator (in the case of oven-dried samples) and promptly dispersed in 10 ml of anhydride to avoid any water uptake from the ambient air. A catalytic amount (0.2 ml) of sulfuric acid was added to the dispersion. The mixture was placed in a closed vial and gently agitated with a rotary mixer. After 24 hours of mixing, the fibers were filtered and washed with deionized water several times until the pH of the filtrate was neutral.

The efficiency of the treatment was evaluated by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) using a Thermo Scientific Smart iTR spectrophotometer and the Omnic Software. The test was performed on both flax and kraft fibers with and without the drying stage (mentioned above) before acetylation. The humidity level in the non-dried condition was between 6% and 8% by weight for both the flax and kraft fibers.

2.4 Evaluation of the wettability of treated fibers

Once kraft and flax fibers were thoroughly washed they were pelletized (Fig. 2) using a hydraulic press at a pressure of 137.9 MPa (20 000 psi). The pellet shape, 13 mm in diameter, was more convenient for the wettability test because the high compaction pressure reduced considerably the porosity so the surface of the sample became flatter and smoother compared to a normal sheet of paper. It was in fact impossible to perform contact angle measurements neither on normal paper handsheets nor on flax pellets because in these cases, the resin absorption was too fast. For flax pellets, a resin penetration test has been used instead as explained in Section 2.7.

The wettability tests were performed on a FTA4000 contact angle analyzer from First Ten Angstrom. The FTA32 image analysis software was used to measure contact angles. The drop shape method consists in measuring the angle between the surface and the tangent to the drop (Fig. 3). Higher affinity (better wettability) between the liquid and the surface is obtained for low angles.

Before conducting any kind of measurement, the surface roughness of flax and kraft fiber pellets was analyzed with a NT1100 profilometer from Veeco and the Vision software. The analyzed surface was 0.25 mm² which represent the area a droplet can cover. Roughness was measured using the Ra parameter which is the arithmetic mean of the distance between successive peaks and cavities. This parameter gives a general indication of the roughness for a given surface.

2.5 Surface properties of kraft fibers

First, the contact angles were measured using droplets of water on kraft fiber pellets to determine the effect of the treatment on the hydrophilicity of kraft fibers. Epoxy resin being non-polar compared to water, this means that more hydrophobic fibers should be more compatible to epoxy resin. These tests were performed only on kraft fibers and not on flax fibers. It was not possible to measure any contact angle on flax because water penetration was too fast in this material, even after it has been pelletized. Kraft fiber pellets were compact enough to allow the formation of a water drop on the surface.

2.6 Wettability of kraft fibers to epoxy resin

The next step was to measure the contact angle of epoxy resin drop on kraft fiber pellets. For these tests, the FTA4000 syringe (Fig. 4) had to be customized because the resin was too viscous to be dispensed by the standard syringe pump. The modification consisted in injecting the resin with a 2-mL plastic syringe through a large 32 gauges needle. The drawback of this method was that the syringe had to be operated manually. It was thus important to repeat each measurement several times to reduce variability. Indeed, when a drop is deposited on the surface, it spreads until it reaches equilibrium. Considering the high viscosity of epoxy resin, it was necessary to wait a few seconds before measuring the contact angle, i.e. long enough to allow the drop to reach equilibrium in terms of contact angle, called the equilibrium angle. To obtain this value, we measured the evolution of the contact angle for the first 15 seconds (Fig. 5) for which resin penetration into fibers was insignificant. This time was established by observing that the volume of resin sitting on the sample surface was constant over this period. Then, by curve fitting the

angle with respect to time, an asymptotic value was obtained for the contact angle after the first 15 seconds and this was considered as the equilibrium angle. Here again, we were unable to perform this test on flax pellets because the resin penetration occurred too rapidly, even for a high viscosity fluid like epoxy, similar to the tests performed with water.

2.7 Wettability testing from spreading velocity and resin penetration for flax fibers

The next tests performed used the same setup as the contact angle measurement tests. First, the spreading velocity was evaluated by measuring the diameter of the drop over time from images obtained with the FTA4000 high speed camera (120 fps). Measurements were taken inside the 15 seconds period before the resin penetration occurred in the pellets. For the same reasons stated before, this test was not possible on flax pellets because resin penetration started too rapidly to obtain reproducible results for the spreading velocity. Finally, the epoxy penetration rate was calculated by measuring the initial volume of the drop and the time needed for a complete absorption by the pellets. This is the only test that was possible to evaluate the effect of acetylation on the wettability of flax pellets. These two approaches (spreading and penetration rates) became complementary to the equilibrium contact angle test for kraft fibers.

Because the penetration is also influenced by the porosity of the material, it was important to measure this parameter. The following equation was used to calculate the porosity for both flax and kraft pellets:

$$Porosity = \frac{V_t - V_f}{V_t} \quad (1)$$

V_t is the total volume of the pellets while V_f is the volume occupied by the fibers obtained by dividing the pellet weight by the fiber density assumed here to be about 1.5 g/cm³ [10,11]. Porosity was found to be higher for the untreated flax and kraft pellets (Table 1). This result means that a higher penetration rate on the treated material would be caused by the chemical affinity between cellulose and treated fibers and not the porosity. Table 1 also shows a higher porosity for flax pellets compared to kraft pellets. Flax fibers being cut in length to prepare the pellets, they were longer than kraft fibers and more difficult to compact uniformly, even for the high

compaction pressure used. A better approach needs to be developed to ensure precise and more reproducible values for the porosity of flax pellets.

3 Results

3.1 Characterization of the modified fibers

The FTIR spectra for untreated, treated-oven dried and treated-air dried kraft fibers are shown in Figure 6. An important peak around 1740 cm^{-1} is first observed for acetylated fibers, representative of the C=O bond of acetyl groups (COCH_3) grafted on the surface of kraft fibers. It shows that the acetylation reaction occurred with a significant amount of acetyl groups present especially for treated air-dried specimen. As expected, for untreated fibers, the peak is absent. On the other hand, a large hydroxyl (-OH) peak is observed around 3330 cm^{-1} for untreated fibers, representative of a strong presence of hydroxyl groups. Considering that the anhydride reacts with hydroxyl groups, it seems that the reaction performed best with treated-air dried specimen while it was not complete for the treated-oven dried specimen.

These results globally mean that the second condition (treated-air dried) shows a considerable improvement in terms of grafting efficiency. As shown in Figure 6, we can observe a much larger peak around 1740 cm^{-1} , representative of a the presence of C=O bonds at the surface of fibers, with no peak at 3330 cm^{-1} . This suggests that the reaction yield is much better when humidity is still present in the fibers. In contact with water, the acetic anhydride becomes acetic acid, which causes the fiber to swell during the reaction. The swelling makes the hydroxyl group more readily available for the anhydride, thus improving the reaction efficiency. These results seem to confirm that a better way to acetylate cellulosic fibers is to avoid complete drying before the reaction is carried out. This means that the drying process, which requires time and energy, can be avoided.

As for the acetylation yield of kraft fibers, the same tendency was obtained for flax fibers (Figure 7), except for the reaction yield which seemed to be lower. This is probably due to the fact that flax fibers still contain extractible substances, i.e. hemicelluloses and lignin, which was not the case

for kraft fibers. These extractible substances tend to be adsorbed on fiber surface making the hydroxyl group more difficult to reach, leading to lower reaction yields. To improve the yield, the lignin and hemicelluloses should be removed with a pre-treatment such as an alkaline treatment [12].

3.2 Water contact angle

As mentioned above, the water contact angle (Fig. 8) was measured on kraft fiber pellets only because water penetration occurred too rapidly on flax pellets. Several tests were performed to reduce the variability of the mean value. The results were $78.3\pm 1.2^\circ$ for acetylated kraft fibers and $59.9\pm 1.9^\circ$ for the untreated kraft fibers. This 19 degrees difference indicates a significant difference on how the water interacts with the surface, showing that the hydrophilic character of kraft fibers is greatly reduced by the treatment.

Because acetic anhydride reacts with the hydroxyl groups at the surface of fibers, a more efficient grafting means less hydroxyl groups available to interact with water. These results confirm the FTIR results presented in Figures 6 and 7. A large reduction of the hydroxyl peak corresponds to the higher contact angle with water, both results indicating a more hydrophobic character of fibers. These results also suggest that acetylation would improve the affinity with epoxy resin because water and epoxy have opposite characters. Water has a much higher polar character than epoxy. This means that acetylation for composite applications would improve the durability of the material by lowering the humidity uptake of fibers.

3.3 Epoxy equilibrium contact angle

The equilibrium contact angle (Fig. 9) of epoxy on acetylated kraft fibers was $23.6\pm 1.3^\circ$ while on untreated fibers it was $30.2\pm 1.3^\circ$. This is in agreement with the results obtained above. By making the kraft fibers hydrophobic, the treatment reduces the affinity to water while increasing that of epoxy. The surface energy is lowered by the treatment. For non-polar liquids like epoxy, lowering the surface energy leads to a better wettability of the surface. As it was the case for water, this test was not possible on flax pellets because of the fast resin penetration.

3.4 Spreading rate of epoxy on kraft fiber pellets

To confirm the affinity between acetylated fibers and epoxy, the variation rate of the drop diameter (or spreading velocity) was measured. Generally, a higher surface roughness reduces the rate at which the droplet diameter increases. We can imagine peaks and cavities as obstacles to liquid progression. Therefore, it was necessary to consider this variable to make sure that a faster spreading would not be caused by a lower roughness. For untreated kraft fibers (Fig. 10) we found a mean Ra value of 0.8354 μm and for acetylated kraft fibers (Fig. 11) we found a mean value of 1.88 μm which is more than twice the value of untreated fibers. These results confirm that a better spreading on acetylated paper will indeed mean a better wettability. For flax pellets, we were unable to measure a mean roughness value. Due to the very high and irregular roughness of the surface, the amplitude of peaks and valleys at the surface exceeded the measurement limits of the equipment (Fig. 12). Nevertheless, it is clear from Figure 12 that the roughness of flax pellets was much higher than that of kraft pellets.

Figure 13 shows that the drop diameter increases more rapidly for acetylated fibers even if the surface roughness is higher (which should normally reduce the spreading velocity). Considering the higher surface roughness of acetylated fibers, this suggests that the kraft fibers, once acetylated, have more affinity with epoxy resin than the untreated ones. This also suggests that during the resin injection phase into an acetylated fiber composite preform (such as in the RTM or resin infusion processes), the resin should flow and wet the fibers more easily and efficiently. This will be discussed in Section 3.5 where the resin penetration rates inside the pellets are compared. The curves of Figure 13 can be modeled with logarithmic equations of the form;

$$D = -A \ln t + B \quad (2)$$

where A and B are constants. The plot of D versus $\ln t$ is a straight line where A is the slope of the line. The derivative of equation 2 being $dD/dt = -A/t$, coefficient A is thus proportional to the spreading velocity of the drop. These coefficients are shown in the bar chart of Figure 14 with the variations obtained for all tests performed. The higher the coefficient, the faster the diameter is progressing on

the surface of the pellet. It is again evident that acetylated kraft fibers produced a faster resin spread.

3.5 Penetration rate of epoxy

The penetration rate of epoxy inside the kraft fiber pellets was finally evaluated. It consists in measuring the initial volume of the resin drop to determine the time required for a complete penetration of the drop into the pellet. With this measure, a mean penetration rate was calculated. For kraft fiber pellets, the difference between treated and untreated samples is very significant as shown in Figure 15. The penetration is about 5.5 times faster for the acetylated fibers. The standard deviations obtained were caused by the fact that each penetration run was very long to complete considering the high resin viscosity. So any small variation in pellets compaction translates into a much larger variation of the penetration rate.

Unlike the contact angle test, the penetration test was possible with flax pellets. As shown in Figure 16, a significant difference is also observed between untreated and acetylated flax fibers. For the acetylated flax the penetration rate was about 2.9 times faster, indicating a better affinity with epoxy. Somehow, this lower ratio is not surprising considering the higher porosities obtained for flax pellets. A higher porosity increases the penetration rate and, combined to the increased wettability induced by the acetylation treatment, the overall effect is a reduction of the penetration rate ratio between acetylated and untreated flax fibers. Globally, these results are in agreement with other results regarding the better wettability of acetylated kraft fibers. The exact influence of porosity needs however to be quantified and this should be done in future works.

Finally, to show the evolution of the drop shape over time, pictures have been taken during the tests. Figure 17 shows the evolution over time of typical epoxy resin drops deposited onto kraft fibers and flax pellets. After 140 seconds, resin penetration into the kraft fibers is still occurring while it is completed for the flax pellet. The absorption into kraft fibers occurs over about 513 seconds, a much longer period of time than flax. Kraft fibers were a lot easier to compact (giving smoother pellet surfaces) considering that they contain almost only cellulose.

Flax fibers contain cellulose but also hemicelluloses and lignin which could affect the flow path of resin and affect the penetration. From a composite point of view and for a given porosity, this penetration improvement should ease the wettability and impregnation of acetylated flax, leading to reduced voids and defects in the final material.

4 Conclusions

In this work, the efficiency of the acetylation reaction at improving the wettability of flax and kraft fiber pellets has been evaluated. The reaction yield has first been evaluated from FTIR analyses. Then, the wettability of flax and kraft fiber pellets has been evaluated by three different approaches using the contact angle test apparatus. First, the contact angle of water drops on kraft fiber pellets revealed that the acetylation treatment increases the hydrophobicity of fibers, which was confirmed after performing the test with epoxy, more hydrophobic and compatible with the treated kraft fibers. These results were confirmed from the spreading velocity and penetration rate tests with the epoxy drop spreading and impregnating the acetylated kraft fiber and flax fiber pellets at faster rates. Based on these results, it is clear that the acetylation treatment leads to a better wettability. Grafting of acetic anhydride onto cellulose lowers the surface energy and increases the affinity between cellulose and epoxy. From a composite point of view, this could contribute to improve the permeability and the mechanical properties of flax/paper/epoxy composites.

5 References

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Fig. 1 - Acetylation of cellulose.

Fig. 2 - Flax and kraft fiber pellets used for the contact angle analysis.

Fig. 3 - Contact angle measurement using the drop shape method.

Fig. 4 - FTA4000 with a custom needle.

Fig. 5 - Graphical technique used to measure the equilibrium contact angle.

Table 1 - Porosity of flax and kraft fibers pellets.

Fibers	Porosity (%)	
	Untreated	Treated
Kraft	36±5	23±3
Flax	75±11	72±9

Fig. 6 – FTIR plots of untreated and treated (acetylated) kraft fibers with oven dried and air dried conditioning.

Fig. 7 – FTIR plots of untreated and treated (acetylated) flax fibers with oven dried and air dried conditioning.

Fig. 8 - Water contact angle on treated (A) and untreated (B) kraft fibers.

Fig. 9 - Epoxy equilibrium contact angle.

Fig. 12 - Typical roughness measurement of flax fibers.

Fig. 10 - Roughness of untreated kraft fibers.

Fig. 13 - Drop diameter as function of time for kraft fibers.

Fig. 11 - Roughness of treated kraft fibers.

Fig. 14 - Logarithmic function coefficient for kraft fibers.

Fig. 15 - Penetration rate of epoxy on kraft fibers.

Fig. 16 - Penetration rate of epoxy on flax.

Fig. 17 - Penetration of epoxy on flax and kraft fibers pellets.